

EDAP+ TN on Quality Assessment of EOS-04

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AMENDMENT RECORD SHEET

The Amendment Record Sheet below records the history and issue status of this document.

ISSUE	DATE	REASON
0.1	04/04/2024	First draft version with preliminary results.
0.2	15/07/2024	First version of the TN delivered to ESA for review.
1.0	20/09/2024	TN updated according to ESA review. First version published on-line.
1.1	05/02/2025	TN updated according to reassessment of elevation antenna pattern after cross-check with data providers

TABLE OF CONTENTS

AMENDMENT RECORD SHEET.....	2
TABLE OF CONTENTS.....	3
1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	5
1.1 References	5
1.2 Glossary	6
1.3 Cal/Val Maturity Matrices	7
1.3.1 Summary Cal/Val Maturity Matrix	7
1.3.2 Validation Cal/Val Maturity Matrix.....	8
2. DATA PROVIDER DOCUMENTATION REVIEW	9
2.1 Product Information	9
2.2 Metrology.....	12
2.3 Product Generation	14
3. MISSION OVERVIEW.....	15
4. EOS-04 DATA ASSESMENT	17
4.1 General feedback on EOS-04 products	17
4.2 Point target data assessment.....	19
4.2.1 Resolution assessment	20
4.2.2 Geolocation assessment	22
4.2.3 Absolute radiometric calibration assessment	24
4.2.4 Summary	24
4.3 Rain Forest data assessment	25
4.4 Doldrums data assessment.....	27
5. EOS-04 AND S-1 INTERCOMPARISON	29
5.1 Mission comparison	29
5.2 Acquisition modes comparison	30
5.3 Products comparison	30
5.3.1 IRF and geolocation comparison.....	30
5.3.2 Geolocation accuracy	31
5.3.3 Rain Forest comparison	31
5.3.4 NESZ comparison.....	32
5.3.5 Interferometric capability comparison.....	34

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1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The results of the preliminary assessment of EOS-04 data quality can be found in the following sections. The main outcomes of the assessment are resumed here below:

- The documentation is OK but, in some cases, (e.g., the product format) more details on the reported parameters could be useful for the users.
- The products metadata report the required information for a high-level interpretation of the data, nevertheless a few issues have been observed and are reported later in the document.
- The description on how to get properly calibrated data is a bit ambiguous. In the documentation it is clearly stated that EOS-04 products are provided in beta-nought, while RISAT-1 products were provided in sigma-nought. In the meta-data there is a dedicated field *<lutApplied>* that for the analysed products was set to sigma (but no information on the meaning of this field is available). Also, in the meta-data 3 different calibration constants are present for beta-, sigma- and gamma-nought. It is recommended to harmonize the product specification and the data content and to include a proper description of the conversion from digital numbers to RADAR observables.
- The main issue with the products is an artifact affecting all the SLC data. An azimuth portion at the edge of the burst is repeated in the other edge. The artifact is not present in the GRD products that are correctly merged.
- The analysis of the IRF parameters from point target data shows that the geometric resolution is in line with the products specification both in range and azimuth direction.
- The assessment of the geolocation accuracy shows that, for SLC products, the Absolute Localisation Error is below the product specification of 50 m (RMSE). The ALE is largely product dependent.
- The GRD localisation accuracy is not feasible due to the low order of the slant to ground polynomial annotated in the GRD products.
- The assessment of Rain Forest products shows that a slight residual slope as a function of the incidence angle is present for SLC products mainly due to some residual beam-to-beam offset, while the profiles are almost flat for GRD products. A residual scalloping profile (0.4 dB peak-to-peak) is observed in the azimuth direction.
- The worst case NESZ level measured over the Doldrums is below the product specification of about 5 dB (-24 dB instead of -19.1 dB).
- The comparison between EOS-04 MRS products and the Sentinel-1 IWS products is reported in the final chapter of the document.

1.1 References

The following is a list of reference documents with a direct bearing on the content of this proposal. Where referenced in the text, these are identified as [RD-n], where 'n' is the number in the list below:

- RD-1. Earth Observation Mission Quality Assessment Framework, EDAP.REP.001, v2.2, December 2022. Available at <https://earth.esa.int/eogateway/documents/20142/37627/Mission-Quality-Assessment-Guidelines-v2.2.pdf/033c703e-02f8-d993-9859-560aeb61d2a0?t=1676561363850>
- RD-2. Earth Observation Mission Quality Assessment Framework - SAR Guidelines, EDAP.REP.060, v1.0, November 2021. Available at:

<https://earth.esa.int/eogateway/documents/20142/37627/SAR+Mission+Quality+Assessment+Guidelines.pdf/a608bb6f-a3e1-0e7b-c652-2812049431cc>

RD-3. EDAP+ TN on Methods and Reference Data for SAR Data Quality Assessments, EDAP+.REP.007, v1.0, March 2023. Available at:

<https://earth.esa.int/eogateway/documents/20142/37627/EDAP%2B.REP.007%20EDAP%2B%20TN%20for%20Methods%20and%20Reference%20Data%20for%20SAR%20Data%20Quality%20Assessments%20v11.pdf/9d8e8d28-025a-1e98-0342-7e644e8fe96a?version=1.0&t=1684419934084>

RD-4. EOS-04 Hand Book, NRSC-DPA-NDC-OCT 2022-TG-0002110-V1.0, available on line at

<https://bhoonidhi.nrsc.gov.in/bhoonidhi/help/helpdocs/missionHandbooks.html>

RD-5. EOS-04 Data Products Formats (July 2023), Version 1.2.4, available on-line at

<https://bhoonidhi.nrsc.gov.in/bhoonidhi/help/helpdocs/prodSpec.html>

RD-6. S-1 Annual Performance Report for 2023, SAR-MPC-0634 – Issue 1.3 – 19/04/2024, on-line document

1.2 Glossary

The following acronyms and abbreviations have been used in this Report.

ALE	Absolute Location Error
CR	Corner Reflector
EAP	Elevation Antenna Pattern
GRD	Stripmap Multi Look Detected
IRF	Impulse Response Function
ISLR	Integrated Side Lobe Ratio
IWS	Interferometric Wide Swath
MRS	Medium Resolution ScanSAR
NESZ	Noise Equivalent Sigma Nought
PSLR	Peak-to-side Lobe Ration
PT	Point Target
RCS	Radar Cross Section
RF	Rain Forest
SLC	Stripmap Single Look Complex

1.3 Cal/Val Maturity Matrices

1.3.1 Summary Cal/Val Maturity Matrix

Data Provider Documentation Review			Validation Summary	Key
Product Information	Metrology	Product Generation		Not Assessed
Product Details	Sensor Calibration & Characterisation	Calibration Algorithm	Measurement Validation Method	Not Assessable
Availability & Accessibility	Geometric Calibration & Characterisation	Geometric Processing	Measurement Validation Results Compliance	Basic
Product Format, Flags & Metadata	Metrological Traceability Documentation	Mission-Specific Processing	Geometric Validation Method	Good
User Documentation	Uncertainty Characterisation		Geometric Validation Results Compliance	Excellent
	Ancillary Data			Ideal
				Not Public

Figure 1-1: Summary Matrix Cal/Val Maturity Matrix

1.3.2 Validation Cal/Val Maturity Matrix

Aresys Detailed Validation			
Measurement		Geometric	
Radiometric stability: EAP compensation and Beam-to-beam calibration Method	Radiometric stability: EAP compensation and Beam-to-beam calibration Results	Spatial Resolution and IRF Analysis Method	Spatial Resolution and IRF Analysis Results
Radiometric stability: Residual Azimuth Scalloping Method	Radiometric stability: Residual Azimuth Scalloping Results	Geolocation Accuracy Method	Geolocation Accuracy Results
Absolute Radiometric Calibration Method	Absolute Radiometric Calibration Results		
Thermal Noise Measurement Method	Thermal Noise Measurement Results		

Key
Not Assessed
Not Assessable
Basic
Good
Excellent
Ideal
Not Public

Figure 1-2: Validation Cal/Val Maturity Matrix

2. DATA PROVIDER DOCUMENTATION REVIEW

2.1 Product Information

Product Details	
Grade: Good	
Justification	<i>Overall, the products include enough information for the correct interpretation of the data. Some of the reported parameters could be made clearer (see also comments on Product Format)</i>
Product Name	<i>Product name is a string of number corresponding to the Work Order ID of the processor. For this reason, it is not possible to easily identify products from their name.</i>
Sensor Name	EOS-04
Sensor Type	C-Band SAR
Mission Type	Single satellite
Mission Orbit	524.87 km SSO (6 AM - descending / 6 PM equatorial crossing) with 17 days repeat cycle.
Product Version Number	The assessed products have been generated with the following processor version: 1.1.03
Product ID	An Image ID is reported in the metadata that includes a numerical ID and a date.
Processing level of product	The ScanSAR Medium Resolution (MRS) mode has been selected for the assessment. Two types of products, all Level 1, have been selected for the assessment which are identified as: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • L1A SLC (Single look, complex, slant range) • L1B GRD (Multi-look, detected, ground range)
Measured Quantity Name	The squared pixel is the radar backscatter section β^0
Measured Quantity Units	m^2
Stated Measurement Quality	Absolute radiometric accuracy: +/- 1 dB (according to RD-4) Requirement for geolocation error: <50m (according to RD-4)
Spatial Resolution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MRS-6 resolution: 27/8.8 m (azimuth - range) • MRS-8 resolution: 33/8.8 m (azimuth - range)
Spatial Coverage	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MRS-6: 160-160 km (azimuth - range) • MRS-8: 160-115 km (azimuth - range)
Temporal Resolution	17 days
Temporal Coverage	Launch: 14 th February 2022 First image: 25 th February 2022 Planned life: 10 years
Point of Contact	GAF AG
Product locator (DOI/URL)	Products received from ISRO (https://www.isro.gov.in/) through GAF AG (https://www.gaf.de/)
Conditions for access and use	The on-line archive provides both open and priced data.

Limitations on public access	ISRO online catalogue (https://bhoonidhi.nrsc.gov.in/bhoonidhi/home.html): registration and acceptance of terms and conditions required. The archive has not been assessed in the framework of EDAP activities.
Product Abstract	SLC: stripmap, single look, complex, slant range. GRD: stripmap, multi-look, detected, ground range (using ellipsoid). Calibration status specified in product metadata.

Availability & Accessibility	
Grade: Not assessed	
Justification	The EOS-04 data used for the assessment have been provided by GAF AG (https://www.gaf.de/) acting as intermediary between ESA and ISRO. ISRO provides a data portal (https://bhoonidhi.nrsc.gov.in/bhoonidhi/home.html) that requires user registration. From a preliminary assessment only L2 products (not part of the present assessment) are available on the portal. No further assessment of the portal was performed. Details on the data access are provided in the EOS-04 mission handbook [RD-4].
Compliant with FAIR principles	N/A
Data Management Plan	N/A
Availability Status	N/A

Product Format	
Grade: Good	
Justification	<p>An overview of the available products is provided in RD-4 whereas the products format is documented in RD-5. The products format document provides a complete list of the parameters included in the metadata but does not provide further details on how to interpret them.</p> <p>A few additional remarks:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reference frame of the provided attitude angles not specified. • Reference frame of orbit State Vectors not specified (latest version of the products is ECEF). • In some cases, time stamps are provided with a wrong number of digits for seconds (e.g., 12:15:5.000 instead of 12:15:05.000) • The section on the bursts is not easy to interpret in terms of vali/invalid lines) • Slant to ground conversion polynomial in GRD products is 2nd order and not accurate enough for a proper conversion.

Product File Format	<p>Product is delivered in the form of a zip file with an unclear naming convention (a string of numbers). The unzipped folder includes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • a product.xml files with the product metadata required to interpret the data • a quick-look file in jpg format for each polarization (in case of ScanSAR SLC data the merged product is shown) • a BAND_META.txt file with some generic details on the product • one *_SlantRange_grid.txt file (for SLC) *_GroundRange_grid.txt (for GRD) file per polarization including a set of ground points (lat/lon) and the corresponding slant range and incidence angle coordinates. • One folder per polarization including the geotiff files with the SAR data (in case of ScanSAR data one file per sub-swath is provided)
Metadata Conventions	ASCII and xml
Analysis Ready Data?	Products analysed here are not ARD

User Documentation		
Grade: Good		
Justification	The EOS-04 handbook provides a good description of the mission and of the available products. The L1 ATBD is not available.	
Document	Reference	QA4ECV Compliant
Product User Guide	EOS-04 handbook available on-line (see [RD-4])	No
ATBD	Not available	N/A

2.2 Metrology

Sensor Calibration & Characterisation	
Grade: Good	
Justification	A description of the EOS-04 calibration and quality assurance strategy is provided in the mission handbook [RD-4]. No official calibration reports are available to the public. A few conference papers/presentations including some calibration methodologies and results can be found on-line.
References	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Calibration and Validation of EOS-04 Hybrid Polarimetric ScanSAR Data, NSCR/ISRO, PolInSAR 2023</i> • <i>EOS-04 (RISAT-1A) Strip and ScanSAR Full-Pol Product Evaluation for Calibration, NSCR/ISRO, CEOS 2023</i> • <i>In-Orbit Performance Assessment Using Internal Instrument and Absolute Calibration of EOS-04, NSCR/ISRO, CEOS 2023</i> • <i>A. A. Kesarkar et al., "Measurement of On-board Azimuth Antenna Patterns for EOS-04 SAR Payload," IGARSS 2023 - 2023 IEEE International Geoscience and Remote Sensing Symposium, Pasadena, CA, USA, 2023</i>
Geometric Calibration & Characterisation	
Grade: Good	
Justification	A description of the EOS-04 calibration and quality assurance strategy is provided in the mission handbook [RD-4]. No official calibration reports are available to the public. A few conference papers/presentations including some calibration methodologies and results can be found on-line.
References	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Calibration and Validation of EOS-04 Hybrid Polarimetric ScanSAR Data, NSCR/ISRO, PolInSAR 2023</i> • <i>EOS-04 (RISAT-1A) Strip and ScanSAR Full-Pol Product Evaluation for Calibration, NSCR/ISRO, CEOS 2023</i> • <i>In-Orbit Performance Assessment Using Internal Instrument and Absolute Calibration of EOS-04, NSCR/ISRO, CEOS 2023</i> • <i>A. A. Kesarkar et al., "Measurement of On-board Azimuth Antenna Patterns for EOS-04 SAR Payload," IGARSS 2023 - 2023 IEEE International Geoscience and Remote Sensing Symposium, Pasadena, CA, USA, 2023</i>
Metrological Traceability Documentation	
Grade: Not Assessable	
Justification	<i>No traceability documentation provided</i>
References	<i>N/A</i>

Uncertainty Characterisation	
Grade: Not Assessable	
Justification	<i>No pixel-level uncertainty characterization is reported in the product.</i>
References	N/A

Ancillary Data	
Grade: Good	
Justification	<i>Ancillary data are provided as xml or ASCII file. The ancillary data are detailed and include information about acquisition, orbit, attitude and processing. The product format document provides a list of the ancillary data but, in some cases, not enough details to correctly interpret them.</i>
References	<i>Ancillary data are described in [RD-5]</i>

2.3 Product Generation

Calibration Algorithm	
Grade: Good	
Justification	<p>A few details on performed SAR processing are reported in the EOS-04 mission handbook [RD-4]. The meta data contain some details about the applied calibration steps including:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Calibration LUT representing the output data quantity (beta, sigma or gamma) • ElevationPatternCorrection flag • RawDataCorrection flag • RadiometricSmoothingPerformed flag • Information on processed bandwidths and applied windows
References	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Product Specification Document [RD-5]

Geometric Processing	
Grade: Basic	
Justification	<p>The SAR data in RADAR coordinates (SLC) are projected into geographical coordinates on WGS84 ellipsoid for GRD products. Conversion from ground to slant is not easy due to the low order of the annotated poly (2nd order). The products include ASCII grids that cannot be easily interpreted.</p>
References	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Product Specification Document [RD-5]

Mission-Specific Processing	
Grade: Not assessed	
Justification	<p>L2 products are described in the mission handbook and products specification documents. No L2 products have been provided for the assessment.</p>
References	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Product Specification Document [RD-5]

3. MISSION OVERVIEW

EOS-04, formerly known as RISAT-1A, is operated by the Indian space agency (ISRO) and was launched in 2022. It is intended as a follow-on mission to RISAT-1 launched in 2012 and is expected to have its twin satellite, RISAT-1B, launched by 2024. EOS-04 is a Low Earth Orbit (LEO) satellite operated in a Sun Synchronous Polar Orbit (SSPO) with 6 AM-6 PM Equatorial Crossing Time (ECT) at an altitude of 524.87 km carrying a Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) payload. The EOS-04 Sar instrument operates at C-band, and can acquire in Stripmap, ScanSAR and potentially Spotlight modes, with spatial resolution ranging from 3 m up to 50 m.

Table 3-1: EOS-04 payload specifications

Parameters	Specifications
Altitude	524.87 km
Orbit	Sun synchronous (6 AM -descending / 6 PM equatorial crossing)
Frequency	5.4 GHz + 37.5 MHz
Polarization Combination	Single / Dual / Full-pol /Hybrid circular polarimetry (Transmit circular, receive linear)
Average DC Input Power	3.8 kW
Pulse width	5 μ s to 25 μ s
Antenna Roll Bias (deg)	$\pm 36^\circ$
Range Coverage (km)	107-659 (either side of flight track)
Look Angle (deg)	11.5-49.6
Incidence Angle (deg)	12.4-55.5

The basic imaging modes for EOS-04 are the following:

- Coarse Resolution scanSAR Mode (CRS): 50 m resolution, 223 km swath, Single, Dual, Circular/ Full-Pol.
- Medium Resolution scanSAR Mode (MRS): 33 m resolution, 160 km swath, Single, Dual, Circular/ Full-Pol.
- Fine Resolution Stripmap Mode-1 (FRS-1): 3 m resolution, 25 km swath, Single, Dual, Circular/ Full-Pol
- Fine Resolution Stripmap Mode-2 (FRS-2): 3 m resolution, 20 km swath, Single, Dual, Circular/ Full-Pol.
- High Resolution Spotlight Mode (HRS): 1 m resolution and 15 km swath, Single, Dual, Circular.

FRS-1 is a conventional Stripmap mode of SAR operation. MRS and CRS are 8 and 12-beam ScanSAR configuration respectively. High Resolution Spotlight mode (HRS) has been added to provide a spotlight image of 10 km \times 15 km with better than 2 m resolution in co and/or cross polarization. Provision is also made for an experimental capability to increase the azimuth extent up to 100 km in HRS mode which is called sliding Spotlight mode. The main characteristics of the acquisition modes are reported in the following table.

Table 3-2: EOS-04 features of operation modes

MODES	FRS-1 (FRS-1 FP)	FRS-2 (FRS-2 FP)	6-beam / 8- beam MRS / CRS	ScanSAR – FP (6/8/12 beam)	HRS
Chirp Bandwidth (MHz)	75	37.5	18.75	18.75	75
PRF (Hz)	2800-3200 (5600-6400)	2800-3200 (5600-6400)	2800-3200	5600-6400	3000-3700
Worst Sigma Naught (dB)	≤ -18	≤ -19	≤ -18	≤ -16	≤ -18
Swath (km)	25(20)	25(20)	115 / 160 / 223	87 / 115 / 168	15
Off-Nadir (km)	100-650 (100-400)	100-650 (100-400)	100-650	100-400	100-650
Slant range resolution (m)	2	4	8	8	2
Ground range resolution (m)	9.3-2.4	18.6-6.3	37.2-9.7	37.2-12.6	9.3-2.4
Azimuth Resolution (m)	3	3	23 / 33 / 50	23 / 33 / 50	1
Polarisation	Single/Dual/ Circular/Full	Single/Dual/ Circular/Full	Single/Dual/ Circular/Full	Single/Dual/ Circular/Full	Single/Dual/ Circular

Different levels of data products have been defined for the mission. The product can either be scene based or mosaic based. The scene wise products can be generated for nominal product levels as well as value added products. All basic Level-0, Level-1 and Level-2 products will be available as for RISAT-1 with some minor changes.

Table 3-3: EOS-04 product levels

Imaging mode	RAW	L1-SLC	L1-Ground Range	L2-Geo-referenced
	(CEOS)	(CEOS & GeoTIFF)	(CEOS & GeoTIFF)	(GeoTIFF)
FRS-1	✓	✓	✓	✓
FRS-2	✓	✓	✓	✓
MRS	✓	✓	✓	✓
CRS	✓	✓	✓	✓
HRS	✓	✓	NA	✓

4. EOS-04 DATA ASSESSMENT

4.1 General feedback on EOS-04 products

Three versions of the EOS-04 products have been analysed in the framework of the EDAP+ assessment. The feedback here provided refers to the last version of the products, generated with the processor version 1.1.03. The main updates from the original version of the products were:

- The conversion of the annotated State Vectors from Earth Centred Inertial to Earth Centred Earth Fixed reference frame, improving the products usability.
- The correction of the inconsistent time zones used in the products.
- The inclusion of the slant-to-ground poly in the GRD annotations.

Here a list of observations on EOS-04 products is reported:

- The product naming based on the Work Order ID is unclear from a user perspective.
- The BAND_META.txt and product.xml files include some overlapping information and could be merged in a single file to keep all information in a single file.
- The large part of the product.xml files is made of the *GeographicInformation* section including a long list of times, pixel coordinates and incidence angles. This information partly overlaps with the one included in the *SlantRange_grid.txt. It could be beneficial for the users providing this information in a single file and possibly not a text one (netcdf format could be used).
- Two *SlantRange_grid.txt files are provided in case of dual pol data even if the information should be the same. The file for GRD products is called *GroundRange_grid.txt but still includes slant range values. Furthermore, the information annotated in the files for GRD products appears to be inconsistent.
- The different ScanSAR beams are tagged with the central looking angle rather than with a beam identifier. This makes the association of the different beams more complex in case of left/right acquisitions.
- The annotation of bursts valid pixels in the SLC products is inconsistent (e.g., the first valid line is set to 0 even if black pixels are included in the image). As an example, for the burst reported in Figure 4-1, the following validity information is reported:
 - firstValidLine=0
 - numValidLines=262
 - linesPerBurst=283
 - firstValidSample=346

Figure 4-1: Sample EOS-04 ScanSAR burst

- The doppler Rate is annotated as a positive value even if the SAR community convention is to use a negative value.
- The annotated slant to ground polynomial is very low order (2nd order), not allowing for a proper ground to slant conversion.
- An artifact can be observed in all the analysed SLC products. A portion of the burst is repeated. An example is shown in the following image. This artifact disappears after the merging of the bursts in the GRD products.

Figure 4-2: Artifact observed in the analysed EOS-04 ScanSAR SLC products. A portion of the data is repeated.

4.2 Point target data assessment

The point target data assessment has been performed on SLC and GRD products acquired over Rosamond and Surat Basin target arrays. The following products were analysed:

- 5 SLC products acquired over Rosamond
- 4 SLC products acquired over Surat Basin

Unfortunately, due to the issue reported above with the ground to slant coordinates conversion, the results of the GRD assessment are inconsistent and not reported here.

A sample IRF analysis for an EOS-04 SLC product is reported in **Figure 4-3**. In **Figure 4-4** the result of a second IRF analysis is reported. In this case an asymmetric azimuth IRF is observed, resulting in a larger geolocation error. This artifact is observed for a few targets and could be related to some processing artifacts.

Figure 4-3: Sample IRF analysis for an EOS-04 SLC product acquired over Rosamond target array.

target_ROS24CR_B0_polarization_HH_slc IRF Analysis

Figure 4-4: Sample IRF analysis for an EOS-04 SLC product acquired over Rosamond target array. An asymmetric azimuth IRF can be observed.

4.2.1 Resolution assessment

The following images represent the results of the azimuth and range resolution assessment for the analysed products acquired over Rosamond and Surat Basin. Each marker in the plots represents a measurement over one of the CRs visible in the data. The resolution is plotted as a function of the incidence angle. The pink dashed lines represent the reference values reported in the products metadata (9.59 m in range and 30.36 m in azimuth).

The following table provides the range and azimuth processing parameters reported in the EOS-04 products. The reference resolution is quite aligned with the theoretical resolution (from the processing parameters) and with the measured resolution. In particular:

- The slant range resolution is expressed as the 3 dB width of the IRF whereas the reference value refers to the full width of the IRF from 0 to 0. The conversion factor for an ideal sinc is 0.886. As expected, no dependency on the incidence angle is observed. Please note that, unlike other sensors, all the ScanSAR beams have the same bandwidth.
- The azimuth resolution is a bit product dependent because the azimuth processed bandwidth changes from product to product. This could explain the apparent dependency of the azimuth resolution with the incidence angle.

Table 4-1: EOS-04 features of operation modes

Parameters	Range	Azimuth
Processed bandwidth	18750000.000000	180 - 210 Hz (product dependent)
Hamming Window	0.7	1

Figure 4-5: Range resolution as a function of the incidence angle for the EOS-04 analysed products (one point per target).

Figure 4-6: Azimuth resolution as a function of the incidence angle for the EOS-04 analysed products (one point per target).

4.2.2 Geolocation assessment

4.2.2.1 SLC assessment

The following images represent the results of the azimuth and range Absolute Localisation Error (ALE) assessment for the analysed products acquired over Rosamond and Surat Basin. Each marker in the plots represents a measurement over one of the CRs visible in the data. The geolocation accuracy declared in the products handbook RD-4 is 50 m (RMSE).

The obtained results are well within the products requirement. Furthermore, the measurement points are clustered per product, suggesting that most of the observed spread comes from non-accurate orbits introducing a product dependent error. The products have been analysed starting from the orbit state vectors annotated in the metadata files. The source of the orbit data for all the analysed products is GPS.

Figure 4-7: Absolute localisation error measured from point target acquisitions over Rosamond and Surat Basin targets array.

4.2.2.2 GRD assessment

Due to the limitations discussed above (low order of the ground to slant polynomials), it was not possible to perform a complete geolocation validation for GRD products. Nevertheless, the provided EOS-04 products were analysed with “non-standard” methods to get a preliminary grasp on the geolocation quality.

In particular, the preliminary assessment focused on a L1B GRD product acquired over the Amazon Rain Forest. The product overlay on Google Earth is reported in Figure 4-8. It was generated starting from the ground corner points reported in the product metadata. Details of the geocoded image are reported in Figure 4-9 for different image positions. A very good match between ground features (rivers) and data is observed, suggesting that a good geolocation performance is reached by EOS-04. This is in line with the observation from point target data acquired over the dedicated calibration sites.

Figure 4-8: Google Earth overlay of an EOS-04 product acquired over Amazon Rain Forest (Image ID 007203083021293086RT2023-06-05).

Figure 4-9: Details of the geocoded QL of an EOS-04 product acquired over Amazon Rain Forest (Image ID 007203083021293086RT2023-06-05). A very good match between ground features (rivers) and data is observed.

4.2.3 Absolute radiometric calibration assessment

Due to the low resolution of the ScanSAR acquisition mode, increasing a lot the clutter level, it was not possible to properly assess the absolute radiometric calibration of the data. Nevertheless, an indirect assessment is performed based on the cross-comparison between S-1 and EOS-04 products over the Rain Forest (see section 5).

4.2.4 Summary

The following tables provide a summary of the quality parameters derived from the analysed point target acquisitions.

Table 4-2: Summary of IRF analysis results. Average of the quality parameters per product

	Product	Az. Res [m]	Slant rg. Res [m]	ALE: azimuth [m]	ALE: slant rg. [m]	PSLR range [dB]	PSLR azimuth [dB]	ISLR range [dB]	ISLR azimuth [dB]
ROSAMOND	244692311	31.525	8.164	-37.904	-7.408	-20.536	-12.749	-15.538	-9.897
	244692321	31.147	8.173	7.010	1.955	-20.154	-12.162	-15.474	-8.642
	244692341	31.880	8.209	5.071	9.131	-17.017	-12.286	-11.012	-8.397
SURAT BASIN	244692411	31.119	8.160	-13.957	-10.935	-15.417	-11.418	-9.001	-6.858
	245917611	32.389	8.116	-13.758	0.363	-16.545	-12.137	-9.965	-7.708
	246069011	32.368	8.211	-21.854	-5.323	-16.774	-12.246	-10.554	-7.777

Table 4-3: Summary of IRF analysis results. Standard deviation of the quality parameters per product

	Product	Az. Res [m]	Slant rg. Res [m]	ALE: azimuth [m]	ALE: slant rg. [m]	PSLR range [dB]	PSLR azimuth [dB]	ISLR range [dB]	ISLR azimuth [dB]
ROSAMOND	244692311	0.273	0.088	15.586	31.132	1.133	0.549	0.939	0.418
	244692321	2.713	0.191	23.106	24.904	1.278	3.219	2.433	4.326
	244692341	1.923	0.208	27.941	17.269	2.126	1.158	2.230	1.309
SURAT BASIN	244692411	3.572	0.269	3.982	0.730	2.207	1.864	2.176	1.723
	245917611	1.469	0.254	1.235	0.908	2.355	1.303	2.219	1.224
	246069011	1.371	0.241	1.413	1.093	2.116	1.392	1.913	1.297

4.3 Rain Forest data assessment

By exploiting data acquired over Rain Forest, under the assumption that the γ^0 is independent from the incidence angle, it is possible to verify the agreement between the patterns exploited for data compensation and the actual patterns by assessing the flatness of the γ^0 profiles.

Figure 4-10 shows the quick-look of one the analysed EOS-04 L1B GRD product. Overall, the QL quality is OK, but some non-ideal features can be already observed. In particular:

- Some jumps between sub-swaths in the elevation (horizontal) direction are clearly observed.
- A residual amplitude modulation in the azimuth (vertical) direction is clearly observed.

Figure 4-10: Quick-look of the GRD EOS-04 product acquired over Amazon Rain Forest (Image ID 007203083021293086RT2023-06-05).

The γ^0 elevation profiles extracted from one SLC and one GRD product (obtained from the same acquisition) are reported in **Figure 4-11** and **Figure 4-12** respectively. The profiles are plotted as a function of the incidence angle (derived from the products annotations). The profiles for the co (HH, blue line) and cross (HV, orange line) polarization channels are reported.

The profiles for the GRD product (**Figure 4-12**) are almost flat, with slight variations in a range of 0.5 dB over 10 degrees of incidence angles, both for co-pol and cross-pol channels. The observed radiometric level is aligned with the level of γ^0 profiles observed with Sentinel-1 that also operates in C-band.

The results are a bit worse for the SLC product (**Figure 4-11**) where a slightly trend is observed, with a ramp of about 0.7 dB over 10 degrees of incidence angles (slope 0.07 dB/deg). The same trend is observed for co and cross-pol channels. The increase trend seems mainly related to beam-to-beam offset between adjacent beams.

Please note that the plots reported for this product are in line to the plots obtained for all the remaining products suggesting that the observed issues are systematic. The results suggest that beam-to-beam calibration for GRD products is better than for SLC products.

Figure 4-11: γ^0 elevation profiles from SLC EOS-04 product 244692111 acquired over Amazon Rain Forest (Image ID 007203083021293086RT2023-06-05).

Figure 4-12: γ^0 elevation profile for co-pol (left) and cross-pol (right) channels from GRD EOS-4 product 244711531 acquired over Amazon Rain Forest (Image ID 007203083021293086RT2023-06-05, same acquisition as above) .

A further analysis that has been performed on the ScanSAR data acquired over Rain Forest is the derivation of the residual scalloping profile. Scalloping is a characteristic of ScanSAR images since the targets at the edge of the bursts (in azimuth direction) are acquired with a different portion of the azimuth antenna pattern w.r.t. to the targets in the middle of the burst, introducing an azimuth dependent gain factor in each burst. This gain is compensated during the processing exploiting a model of the azimuth antenna pattern. After scalloping compensation, each burst is expected to be flat in the azimuth direction.

Figure 4-13 shows, on the left, the azimuth profile of a portion (corresponding to the last sub-swath) of the EOS-4 product over the Rain Forest. On the right, a detail of the profile is reported. A clear modulation of the data amplitude can be observed and could be related

to a non-perfect de-scalloping of the data. This is also quite clearly observed in the quick look above.

Figure 4-13: (Left) Azimuth profile of a portion (corresponding to the last sub-swath) of the EOS-4 product over the Rain Forest. (Right) Detail of the profile.

4.4 Doldrums data assessment

The thermal noise level of a SAR image is an important quality parameter. Furthermore, the knowledge of the thermal noise level can enable the possibility to perform de-noising, i.e., subtracting the radiometric bias introduced by the noise on the SAR data. The quality parameter related to the thermal noise level is the Noise Equivalent Sigma Zero (NESZ), corresponding to the σ^0 value of a target resulting in a SNR equal to 1.

The thermal noise level can be measured from data acquired over areas with no or low backscatter such as calm sea like the Pacific Doldrums. Figure 4-14 shows the NESZ profile of an EOS-4 product acquired over Pacific Doldrums. As expected, the NESZ profile is modulated from the radiometric corrections (mainly the Elevation Antenna Pattern) applied by the SAR processor. The measured NESZ level is included in the range from -29 dB to -24 dB, well below the declared noise level of -19.1 as reported in the product annotations. The reported result is consistent throughout all the analysed products over Doldrums.

Figure 4-14: NESZ profiles measured from the EOS-4 product over the Doldrums.

5. EOS-04 AND S-1 INTERCOMPARISON

A high-level intercomparison between EOS-04 and S-1 characteristics is here reported. The comparison is performed in terms of:

- Mission parameters
- Acquisition modes parameters
- Products quality results

5.1 Mission comparison

The following table provides a comparison between the main mission parameters of EOS-04 and Sentinel-1.

Table 5-1: EOS-04 vs Sentinel-1 mission's parameters

Parameters	EOS-4	Sentinel-1
Orbit		
Type	Sun synchronous polar	Sun synchronous polar
Altitude	526.7 km - 543.4 km	697.73 - 724.98 km
Inclination	97.6°	98.18°
Period	95.2 minutes	98.6 minutes
Repetition cycle	17 days	12 days
Orbits per cycle	257	175
Instrument		
Frequency	5.4 GHz	5.405 GHz
Polarization Combination	Single / Dual / Full-pol /Hybrid circular polarimetry (Transmit circular, receive linear)	Single / Dual polarimetry
Max bandwidth	75 MHz	100 MHz
Tx power	4650 W	4646.6 W
Operation duty cycle	12 minutes per orbit	25 minutes per orbit
PRF range	2800-3200 HZ 5600-6400 HZ (full pol)	1400 – 2000 Hz
Acquisition		
Attitude Steering	Yaw steering	Total Zero Doppler steering
Antenna Roll Bias	± 36°	28.7° - 30.24° roll-steering law as a function of sensor altitude.
Look direction	Left/Right	Right
Look Angle	11.5-49.6	16.4-41.2 (EW)
Incidence Angle (deg)	12.4-55.5	18.2-47.0 (EW)
Acquisition Modes	Spotlight, Stripmap and ScanSAR	Stripmap, TopSAR and Wave

The two satellites have a quite different orbit in terms of altitude and repetition cycle. The carrier frequency is quite similar. EOS-04 has full polarimetric capability, whereas Sentinel-1 can only acquire dual pol data. The peak power is aligned while the orbit duty cycle of Sentinel-1 is two times the one of EOS-04. EOS-04 can acquire both on the right and on the left side (Sentinel-1 is only right looking).

5.2 Acquisition modes comparison

The following table provides a comparison between the parameters of the main acquisition modes for EOS-04 and Sentinel-1, namely:

- Medium Resolution ScanSAR Mode (MRS) for EOS-04
- Interferometric Wide Swath TopSAR Mode (IWS) for Sentinel-1

Table 5-2: Comparison of EOS-04 MRS and Sentinel-1 IWS acquisition modes

Parameters	EOS-4 Medium Resolution ScanSAR (MRS)	Sentinel-1 Interferometric Wide Swath (IWS)
Acquisition mode	ScanSAR	TopSAR
Number of beams	8	3
Swath width	160 km (115 km for full pol)	250 km
Incidence angles	12.4° - 55.5° (actual range is product dependent, e.g., 32.4°-44.2°)	29.1° - 46.0°
Chirp bandwidth	18.5 MHz (fixed for all sub-swaths)	56.5 / 48.3 / 42.8 MHz
Ground range resolution	37.2-9.7 m (depends on incidence angle of acquisition)	5 m
Azimuth resolution	33 m	22 m
NESZ	< -18 dB	< -22 dB

5.3 Products comparison

The present section provides a high-level comparison of the results of the quality checks performed over EOS-04 and S-1 products. The EOS-04 results are documented in the present report (see sections above). The S-1 quality checks are continuously performed by the SAR MPC (<https://sar-mpc.eu/>) and documented in the S-1 annual reports [RD-6].

5.3.1 IRF and geolocation comparison

The results of the point targets assessment for EOS-04 are reported in Sections 4.2.1 and 4.2.4. A comparison of the IRF parameters is reported in Table 5-3. S-1 IWS mode has a better resolution both in range and azimuth direction. The resolution cell area is around 260 square meters for EOS-04 MRS while is 76 square meters (worst case (IW3) for S-1 IWS. The ground resolution cell area is around 100 square meters for S-1 IWS, while it is largely variable (from 307 to 1180 square meters depending on the incidence angle) for EOS-04 MRS.

Regarding the side lobe levels, they are in line with the configuration parameters used for processing. The side lobe levels for EOS-04 are slightly higher than the expected. This could be because the clutter level is too high introducing a bias in the results. The range windows for the two sensors are similar. On the other hand, the azimuth window is quite different because EOS-04 makes use of a Hamming parameter equal to 1 (box car). This results in a better resolution but worse side lobe levels.

Table 5-3: Comparison of resolution and side lobe levels for EOS-04 MRS and Sentinel-1 IWS acquisition modes

Parameters	EOS-4 - MRS	Sentinel-1 - IWS
Range Hamming window	0.7	0.75
Azimuth Hamming window	1	0.7 / 0.75 / 0.75
Range resolution	8.17 m	2.67 / 3.11 / 3.51 m
Azimuth resolution	31.73 m	21.75 / 21.79 / 21.69 m
Range PSLR	-17.74 dB	-20.60 / -19.97/ -20.66 dB
Azimuth PSLR	-12.17 dB	-23.51 / -20.83 / -20.86 dB

5.3.2 Geolocation accuracy

The results of the geolocation accuracy assessment for EOS-04 are reported in Section 4.2.2. As discussed, the geolocation accuracy requirement for EOS-04 is quite coarse, i.e., better than 50 m. This is observed from the reported results that change a lot (several meters) from one product to the other. The observed variations are in any case below the product requirement.

For information, the geolocation accuracy measured over corner reflectors from Surat Basin during 2023 (108 products) for Sentinel-1 IWS is reported in the following table. Two values are reported:

- The uncorrected value is the value as measured from the S-1 products without implementing any additional correction.
- The refined value is the value obtained including the following corrections:
 - Usage of most accurate orbit.
 - Tropospheric delay correction.
 - Ionospheric delay correction.
 - Targets position corrected for geodynamics.
 - Correction of processor non-ideal behaviour.

Table 5-4: Sentinel-1 IWS geolocation accuracy

Geolocation	Range	Azimuth
Uncorrected	-3.565 ± 0.369 m	2.124 ± 0.857 m
Refined	0.059 ± 0.058 m	-0.140 ± 0.292 m

The Sentinel-1 geolocation accuracy is much better for Sentinel-1 w.r.t. EOS-04.

5.3.3 Rain Forest comparison

The results of the radiometric accuracy assessment for EOS-04 products acquired over Rain Forest are reported in Section 4.3. The main outcome of the analysis suggests that:

- A slight slope in the γ^0 profiles as a function of the incidence angle can be observed for SLC products (about 0.07 dB/deg) mainly due to radiometric jumps between sub-swaths.
- For GRD products, the resulting γ^0 profiles are almost flat, showing minor jumps between sub-swaths.

As a comparison, the quick look of a S-1 TopSAR IW DV product acquired over Amazon Rain Forest (data take ID 644A5, 30th December 2023) is reported in **Figure 5-1**. This is a

RGB image combining the co and cross-pol channels of the data, but no evident jump or slope can be noticed. The corresponding γ^0 profiles are reported in **Figure 5-2** for the co (left) and cross (right) polarization channels. The colours represent the 3 different sub-swaths. The profiles are flat and well aligned. Please note that radiometric level of Sentinel-1 and EOS-04 data over Amazon rain Forest is very similar (around -6.5 dB for co-pol and around -12.5 dB for cross-pol).

Figure 5-1: Quick look of a S-1 TopSAR IW DV product acquired over Amazon Rain Forest (data take ID 644A5, 30th December 2023).

Figure 5-2: γ^0 elevation profiles of co-pol (left) and cross-pol (right) channels of a S-1 TopSAR IW DV product acquired over Amazon Rain Forest (data take ID 644A5, 30th December 2023).

5.3.4 NESZ comparison

The results of the thermal noise level assessment for EOS-04 products acquired over Doldrums are reported in Section 4.4. For a comparison, the NESZ level measured from a Sentinel-1 TopSAR IW DH product (HV polarization) acquired over Doldrums (data take ID 05C340, 04th April 2023) is reported in **Figure 5-3**. The overall NESZ level spans from about -25 to about -30 dB and is only slightly lower than the level measured for EOS-04.

Figure 5-3: NESZ level for a TopSAR IW DH product (HV polarization) acquired over Doldrums (data take ID 05C340, 04th April 2023).

5.3.5 Interferometric capability comparison

Sentinel-1 mission has been designed to ensure the possibility to generate SAR interferograms for any repeat pass over the same area. This is possible thank to:

- A very good orbit control, ensuring an interferometric baseline much lower than the critical baseline.
- A very good synchronization strategy ensuring a burst synchronization better than 5 ms (mission requirement).

A sample S-1 interferogram generated over Salar de Uyuni, a very coherent area ideal for SAR interferograms quality assessment, is shown in the following image.

Figure 5-4: Sample Sentinel-1 interferogram generated over Salar de Uyuni, a very coherent area ideal for SAR interferograms quality assessment.

The burst synchronization is a strong requirement also for ScanSAR interferometry, whereas it is not needed for instance for Stripmap interferometry. This means that the generation of SAR interferograms should be feasible for FRS-1 and FRS-2 modes, whereas for CRS and MRS modes, based on ScanSAR acquisition mode, an assessment of the burst synchronization is required.

Considering the MRS mode assessed in the framework of the EDAP activity, the following considerations apply:

- The MRS burst cycle length (about 0.7 s) is much shorter than the burst cycle length of the S-1 TopSAR IW mode (about 2.7 s).
- The burst duration is even shorter considering that MRS implements 8 beams whereas TopSAR IW only 3.
- A very strict burst synchronization, better than the burst duration, i.e., better than 0.1 s is required to generate a good SAR interferogram.
- No information is available if any burst synchronization strategy is implemented at mission level for EOS-04. If nothing is implemented, it can be assumed that the

burst start times are uniformly distributed and hence about 1 acquisition over 8 should show some degree of synchronization. A few of the good pairs could also show good synchronization. The numbers could be much better if burst synchronization is enforced at mission level.

- The data provide time annotations on the focused bursts, but not on the original sensing time of the bursts. This would be very useful for the users to derive the original burst synchronization and properly filter the data to improve the SAR interferograms quality.

Finally, it is worth noting that the artefacts observed in the SLC products (see section 4.1) will prevent the generation of good quality interferograms.

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